

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

SYNTHESIS, CHARACTERIZATION, ANTIMICROBIAL, THEORETICAL AND *IN-SILICO* STUDIES OF NOVEL PIPERIDINE FUSED PYRAZOLE DERIVATIVES

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ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 23/01/2024

Available online

05/02/2024

Keywords

Cyclization,

Piperidine Fused Pyrazole,

Dft,

Electropotential Maps (Emp)

Molecular Docking,

Molecular Dynamics

Simulation.

ABSTRACT

The present study deals with the synthesis of a series of novel analogues based on piperidine fused pyrazolone core 6a-f and explore its potential as novel anti-bacterial agents via *invitro* & *insilico* studies. The synthesised compounds were analysed using spectroscopic techniques such as ¹H NMR and LC-MS techniques. Major highlight involves the cyclisation reaction of tert-butyl- 4-methyl 3-oxopiperidine-1,4-dicarboxylate with the hydrazine component to access the privileged piperidine fused pyrazolone scaffold. This scaffold was further treated with HCl to remove the amine protecting group and subsequently reacted with isocyanates to deliver the final products containing carboxamide linkage in excellent yields. Density functional theory (DFT) calculations were performed to determine various molecular properties of the synthesized compounds. Based on the reactive sites explored by the molecular electrostatic potential maps, molecular docking and molecular dynamic simulations performed to study the inhibition activity of the compounds, *invitro* analysis found to be compounds exhibited good Zone of Inhibition at 200µg/mL of concentration.

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Please cite this article in press as **Dr Sunil K** et al. Synthesis, Characterization, Antimicrobial, Theoretical and *in-Silico* Studies of Novel Piperidine Fused Pyrazole Derivatives. *Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*.2024:14(01).

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INTRODUCTION

Pyrazolone derivatives are an imperative class of heterocyclic compounds that occur in many drugs. They represent an interesting template for combinatorial and medicinal chemistry due to their simple preparation and wide biological applications [1]. The presence of heterocyclic frameworks in medicinally relevant molecules containing biological importance such as material science, and agrochemicals, apices its significance [2-6]. Among the various (hetero) aromatic architectures, the pyrazolone core displays a wide range of applications in diverse fields. Consequently, the synthesis of diversely functionalized molecules containing a pyrazolone core is of immense potential for various applications [7-8]. A wide range of biological activities, including anti-microbial, anti-fungal, anti-tubercular, anti-inflammatory, anti-convulsant, anti-cancer, anti-viral, angiotensin-converting enzyme (ACE) inhibitory, neuroprotective, cholecystokinin-1 receptor antagonist, and estrogen receptor (ER) ligand activity, have been reported for pyrazolone derivatives [9-13]. Additionally, the fact that several FDA-approved medications contain this pyrazolonepharmacophore moiety emphasizes its significance in the field of medicinal chemistry [14-21]. Numerous pyrazolone derivatives are used as nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory medications [22], including oxyphenbutazone (anti-inflammatory, antipyretic), phenylbutazone (anti-inflammatory, antipyretic) [23], metamizole or dipyrone (analgesic and antipyretic) [24], aminopyrine or aminophenazone (anti-inflammatory, antipyretic, and analgesic) [25], phenylbutazone (anti-inflammatory, antipyretic mainly used in osteoarthritis, rheumatoid arthritis, spondylitis, Reiter's disease) [26], sulfapyrazone (chronic gout) [27], and oxyphenbutazone (antipyretic, analgesic, anti-inflammatory, mild uricosuric) [28].

Many of the heterocyclic compounds and Schiff base derivatives synthesized by the pyrazolone group have high biological activity [14-20]. In addition to their biological properties, pyrazolones are important intermediates in chemical synthesis [21]. The condensation of aldehydes with 3-methyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone using various catalysts (acetic acid, piperidine, sodium dodecyl sulfate, ETBA, and silica-bonded S-sulfonic acid among others) is a recognized route to prepare 4,4'-(arylmethylene)bis(1H-pyrazol-5-ols). Li et al. developed a solid-state condensation procedure for the synthesis of 4,4'-(arylmethylene)bis(1H-pyrazol-5-ols) [22,23]. Furthermore, Bai and coworkers informed its synthesis under microwave irradiation in the absence of a catalyst [24]. Considering the biological relevance of these and pharmaceutically relevant core, our research program aimed at synthesizing novel pyrazolone-based analogues, we were interested in synthesizing some piperidine fused pyrazolone derivatives as potential anti-bacterial agents. Accordingly, we initiated our synthesis starting from tetrahydro-4H-pyran-4-one which was treated with (tert-Butoxy carbonyl) hydrazine at room temperature in methanol to furnish the tetrahydro-4H-pyran-4-ylidene-1,1-dimethylethylester in excellent yields. The structure of this biologically important intermediate was confirmed by ¹H, and mass spectral analysis. Further, computational studies were employed to get further insights into the molecular properties of the compounds. The biologically important pharmacophore was then used as a starting point for performing late-stage diversification. In this paper, we report the use of acid chlorides on this piperidine-fused pyrazolone scaffold to access the respective amide analogues in good yields. The synthesized compounds were explored for their anti-bacterial activities using in-silico studies such as molecular docking and dynamics simulation studies.

Experimental

All the chemicals were purchased from the Sigma Aldrich and are used as it is without any further purification. For column chromatography, Silica gel was procured from Merck Pvt. Ltd., The synthesis of the titled compound is given in scheme 1, and the corresponding nomenclature is used in this paper. The melting point was recorded in the capillary tube on an electrothermal apparatus, the ¹H was recorded using Bruker spectrometer of 400 MHz. The chemical shifts (δ) were recorded in parts per million using methanol -d₆ as the solvent and TMS an internal reference. The LC-MS spectra were recorded on Agilent spectrometer

Procedure for the synthesis of tert-butyl 3-oxo-2-(tetrahydro-2H-pyran-4-yl)-2,3,4,5-tetrahydro-1H-pyrazolo[3,4-c]pyridine-6(7H)-carboxylate (3)

A mixture of (Tetrahydro-2H-pyran-4-yl)hydrazine (1) (1.7g, 11mmol) 1-tert-butyl 4-methyl 3-oxopiperidine-1,4-dicarboxylate (2) (2.92g, 11mmol) was taken in 50ml of EtOH along with Triethyl amine (4 mL, 50 mmol) and allowed to stir at 60°C for 6h, upon completion the reaction mixture was diluted with 100 ml EtOAc, washed with brine solution then dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄, filtered and concentrated under reduced pressure to yield crude product, which was further purified using column chromatography, to afford tert-butyl 3-oxo-2-(tetrahydro-2H-pyran-4-yl)-2,3,4,5-tetrahydro-1H-pyrazolo[3,4-c]pyridine-6(7H)-carboxylate (3) (3.5 g, 99%).

Procedure for the synthesis of 2-(tetrahydro-2H-pyran-4-yl)-4,5,6,7-tetrahydro-1H-pyrazolo[3,4-c]pyridin-3(2H)-one (4)

Tert-butyl 3-oxo-2-(tetrahydro-2H-pyran-4-yl)-2,3,4,5-tetrahydro-1H-pyrazolo[3,4-c]pyridine-6(7H)-carboxylate (3) (3.5 g, 10mmol) in DCM (50 ml) was treated with Dioxane-HCl (25 ml) was stirred at r.t. for 0.5h. The solvent was evaporated to afford HCl salt of 1-(terhydro-2H-pyran-4-yl)-1,2,4,5,6,7-hexahydro-3H-pyrazolo[3,4-c]pyridine-3-one (4) with good yield (2.7 g, 99%), recrystallized using hot EtOH which was used for next step directly.

Procedure for the synthesis of 2-(tetrahydro-2H-pyran-4-yl)-4,5,6,7-tetrahydro-1H-pyrazolo[3,4-c]pyridin-3(2H)-onecarboxamide derivatives (6a-f)

HCl salt of 1-(tetrahydro-2H-pyran-4-yl)-1,2,4,5,6,7-hexahydro-3H-pyrazolo[3,4-c]pyridine-3-one (4) (11mmol) was treated with different appropriate isocyanates (5a-f)(11 mmol) in DCM (5ml) for 2h at rt in presence of triethyl amine (0.3 ml, 5 mmol), the reaction was monitored by TLC using nhexane:EA 7:3 solvent system, upon completion reaction mixture was diluted with 10 ml DCM, washed with brine solution (10ml) then dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄, filtered and concentrated under reduced pressure to yield crude product which was further purified by preparative chromatography to give final compounds (6a-f) in good yield of 85-90%. The chemical structure of the synthesized compound was established by HNMR and Mass spectral analysis.

Reagents & Conditions: i)EtOH, TEA, 6h, 60°C
 ii) DCM, Dioxane-HCl, 0.5, rt
 iii) DCM, TEA, 2h, rt

Synthesis of Piperidine Fused Pyrazole derivatives (6a-f).

2,3,4,5-tetrahydro-1-(tetrahydro-2H-pyran-4-yl)-3-oxo-N-(pyridin-3-yl)-1H-pyrazolo[3,4-c]pyridine-6(7H)-carboxamide (6a):
C₆ON₂H

White solid, Yield: 91 %; Melting point: 76.1-76.4°C; ¹H NMR (400MHz, δppm, MeOD-d₆): 1H NMR: δ 0.91 (t, J= 7.3 Hz, 3H), 1.71 (d, J= 7.3 Hz, 2H), 1.93-2.10 (4H, 2.02 (dd, J= 11.9, 6.8, 6.5, 2.8 Hz), 2.02 (dd, J= 11.9, 6.8, 6.5, 2.8 Hz)), 2.17 (2H, t, J= 7.4 Hz), 2.54 (2H, dd, J= 14.5, 7.1, 3.0 Hz), 3.44-3.63 (6H, 3.52 (ddd, J= 13.4, 7.1, 3.1 Hz), 3.55 (dt, J = 7.9, 6.5 Hz), 3.57 (dt, J = 7.9, 2.8 Hz)), 3.88-4.07 (3H, tt, J = 10.2, 3.5 Hz), 4.00 (d, J = 17.0 Hz)). Elemental analysis. Calcd. C: 61.41%, H: 7.90%, N: 14.32% and O: 16.36%, LC-MS: m/z (%) = 344.4 ([M+H]⁺, cal. 343.38).

2,3,4,5-tetrahydro-1-(tetrahydro-2H-pyran-4-yl)-3-oxo-N-p-tolyl-1H-pyrazolo[3,4-c]pyridine-6(7H)-carboxamide (6b):
C₈ONH₈

White solid, Yield: 97 %; Melting point: 77.6-78.1°C; ¹H NMR (400MHz, δppm, MeOD-d₆): 1H NMR: δ 1.04 (3H, t, J = 7.3 Hz), 1.93-2.10 (4H, 2.02 (dddd, J = 11.9, 6.8, 6.5, 2.8 Hz), 2.02 (dddd, J = 11.9, 6.8, 6.5, 2.8 Hz)), 2.26 (2H, q, J = 7.3 Hz), 2.56 (2H, ddd, J = 14.5, 7.1, 3.0 Hz), 3.46-3.63 (6H, 3.54 (ddd, J = 13.4, 7.1, 3.0 Hz), 3.55 (dt, J = 7.9, 6.5 Hz), 3.57 (dt, J = 7.9, 2.8 Hz)), 3.88-4.07 (3H, 3.95 (t, J = 10.2, 3.5 Hz), 4.00 (d, J = 17.0 Hz)). Elemental analysis. Calcd. C: 60.20%, H: 7.58%, N: 15.04% and O: 17.18%, LC-MS: m/z (%) = 357.5 ([M+H]⁺, cal. 356.42)

2,3,4,5-tetrahydro-1-(tetrahydro-2H-pyran-4-yl)-N-(4-(methylsulfonyl)phenyl)-3-oxo-1H-pyrazolo[3,4-c]pyridine-6(7H)-carboxamide (6c): C₈O₃SNH₈

White solid, Yield: 93 %; Melting point: 70.1-70.5°C; ¹H NMR (400MHz, δppm, MeOD-d₆): ¹H NMR: δ 1.11 (6H, d, J = 6.9 Hz), 1.93-2.10 (4H, 2.02 (dd, J = 11.9, 6.8, 6.5, 2.8 Hz), 2.02 (dd, J = 11.9, 6.8, 6.5, 2.8 Hz)), 2.40 (1H, sept, J = 6.9 Hz), 2.56 (2H, ddd, J = 14.5, 7.1, 3.0 Hz), 3.41-3.63 (6H, 3.49 (ddd, J = 13.4, 7.1, 3.0 Hz), 3.55 (dt, J = 7.9, 6.5 Hz), 3.57 (dt, J = 7.9, 2.8 Hz)), 3.88-4.07 (3H, 3.95 (tt, J = 10.2, 3.5 Hz), 4.00 (d, J = 17.0 Hz)), Elemental analysis. Calcd. C: 61.41%, H: 7.90%, N: 14.32% and O: 16.36%, LC-MS: m/z (%) = 421.6 ([M+H]⁺, cal. 420.48).

N-(4-chloro-3-fluorophenyl)-2,3,4,5-tetrahydro-1-(tetrahydro-2H-pyran-4-yl)-3-oxo-1H-pyrazolo[3,4-c]pyridine-6(7H)-carboxamide (6d): C₇ONClFH₄

White solid, Yield: 96 %; Melting point: 69.2-70.0°C; ¹H NMR (400MHz, δppm, MeOD-d₆): ¹H NMR: δ 0.73-0.91 (4H, 0.82 (dd, J = 8.1, 7.8, 7.7, 7.5 Hz), 0.82 (dd, J = 8.1, 7.8, 7.7, 7.5 Hz)), 1.60 (1H, tt, J = 8.1, 7.5 Hz), 1.93-2.10 (4H, 2.02 (dd, J = 11.9, 6.8, 6.5, 2.8 Hz), 2.02 (dd, J = 11.9, 6.8, 6.5, 2.8 Hz)), 2.56 (2H, dd, J = 14.5, 7.1, 3.0 Hz), 3.43-3.63 (6H, 3.51 (dd, J = 13.4, 7.1, 3.0 Hz), 3.55 (dt, J = 7.9, 6.5 Hz), 3.57 (dt, J = 7.9, 2.8 Hz)), 3.95 (1H, tt, J = 10.2, 3.5 Hz), 4.09 (2H, d, J = 17.0 Hz). Elemental analysis. Calcd. C: 61.84%, H: 7.27%, N: 14.42% and O: 16.47%, LC-MS: m/z (%) = 395.2 ([M+H]⁺, cal. 394.83).

2,3,4,5-tetrahydro-1-(tetrahydro-2H-pyran-4-yl)-N-(1-methyl-1H-indol-6-yl)-3-oxo-1H-pyrazolo[3,4-c]pyridine-6(7H)-carboxamide (6e): C₁₀ON₂H₅

White solid, Yield: 90 %; Melting point: 80.5-80.7°C; ¹H NMR (400MHz, δppm, MeOD-d₆): ¹H NMR: δ 1.85-2.17 (4H, 1.94 (ddt, J = 11.9, 10.2, 6.5 Hz), 2.09 (ddt, J = 11.9, 3.5, 2.8 Hz)), 2.31 (3H, s), 2.57 (2H, ddd, J = 14.5, 7.1, 3.0 Hz), 3.40-3.63 (6H, 3.48 (ddd, J = 13.4, 7.1, 3.0 Hz), 3.56 (ddd, J = 7.9, 6.5, 2.8 Hz), 3.56 (ddd, J = 7.9, 6.5, 2.8 Hz)), 3.88-4.13 (3H, 3.95 (tt, J = 10.2, 3.5 Hz), 4.06 (d, J = 17.0 Hz)), 7.17 (2H, ddd, J = 8.5, 1.2, 0.5 Hz), 7.85 (2H, ddd, J = 8.5, 1.7, 0.5 Hz). Elemental analysis. Calcd. C:66.84%, H:6.79%, N:12.31% and O:14.06%, LC-MS: m/z (%) = 396.6 ([M+H]⁺, cal. 395.45).

N-(4-cyanophenyl)-2,3,4,5-tetrahydro-1-(tetrahydro-2H-pyran-4-yl)-3-oxo-1H-pyrazolo[3,4-c]pyridine-6(7H)-carboxamide (6f): C₈ON₂H₅

White solid, Yield: 97 %; Melting point: 78.1-78.6°C; ¹H NMR (400MHz, δppm, MeOD-d₆): ¹H NMR: δ 1.85-2.17 (4H, 1.94 (dt, J = 11.9, 10.2, 6.5 Hz), 2.09 (dt, J = 11.9, 3.5, 2.8 Hz)), 2.56 (2H, ddd, J = 14.5, 7.1, 3.0 Hz), 3.41-3.63 (6H, 3.49 (dd, J = 13.4, 7.1, 3.0 Hz), 3.56 (dd, J = 7.9, 6.5, 2.8 Hz), 3.56 (dd, J = 7.9, 6.5, 2.8 Hz)), 3.88-4.12 (3H, 3.95 (t, J = 10.2, 3.5 Hz), 4.05 (d, J = 17.0 Hz)), 7.54 (2H, dd, J = 8.7, 1.3, 0.5 Hz), 7.73 (2H, dd, J = 8.7, 1.8, 0.5 Hz). Elemental analysis. Calcd. C:66.84%, H:6.79%, N:12.31% and O:14.06%, LC-MS: m/z (%) = 367.4 ([M+H]⁺, cal. 367.4).

Quantum Theory of Atoms in Molecules

To understand the various topological features exhibited by the compounds, their electron density were examined using the Bader's Atoms in Molecules theory [25-26], employed in the Multiwfn program [27]. This analysis allows to understand and provides us with a quantitative explanation of the bonds and the electronic structure of the atoms in the molecules. Further, to investigate the attractive and repulsive interaction exhibited by the compound RDG based isosurface analysis was performed. The color-filled RDG isosurfaces specify the types of interactions, blue regions indicates the strong hydrogen interaction, van der Waals type of interactions are shown by the green regions, and the strong repulsion or steric interactions are shown by the red colour. The isosurface plots of the molecules are carried out using the visual molecular dynamics software [28].

Molecular docking studies

Antibiotic resistance is one of the major potential threats to human health, especially for the developing countries. Due to the diminished efficacy of antibiotics as a treatment for infections, this results in longer hospital stays and higher death rates for those with infectious diseases [29]. Wide spread antibiotic resistance has been recognized in infectious Escherichia coli (E. coli) bacteria isolated from human, animal and environmental sources. Therefore, it is necessary to investigate the new drug and target to inhibit the growth of E. coli. *Oxidoreductases* is an enzyme of E. coli that catalyse the reduction of riboflavin, FMN and FAD by NADPH and NADH are called NAD(P)H: *flavinoxidoreductases* or *flavinreductases*. The reduction of riboflavin, FMN and FAD by flavinreductases is an important biochemical process that plays a critical role in various metabolic pathways [30, 31]. Inhibitors targeting flavinreductases/oxidoreductases may lead to inhibit E. coli growth and be used to treat infection indicating flavinreductases that is a promising target for the treatment of bacterial infections.

The antibacterial properties of novel pyridine fused pyrazole were investigated using molecular docking analysis. In order to assess substrate-binding pocket of the protein between the compounds and amino acid residues of flavinreductase (PDB ID: 3SVL) from Escherichia coli, molecular docking investigation was performed using MGL tools 1.5.6 with Auto Dock Vina (ADV) software [32]. A three-dimensional structure of flavinreductase enzyme was retrieved by RCSB protein data bank in PDB format. To prepare the protein structure Biovia Discovery Studio-2019 (BDS) visualizer [33] was used. The non-polar hydrogen atoms were subsequently added utilising ADV tool also energy will be minimised. Further, the structures of 6a-f were drawn and used as input. The compounds were prepared and optimised. The PDBQT format files of the prepared protein and compounds 6a-f are used. The grid box was generated with various dimensions of the XYZ centre by targeting the active site of flavinreductase. Through ADV tool, associations between both the chosen compounds and flavinreductase protein their binding score, binding energy and types of interactions were predicted then which are visualized by BDS visualizer [34].

Molecular dynamics simulation

The molecular dynamics simulation was performed for the ligand-protein complex for a period of 100 ns using the Desmond version 3.8 (Schrodinger suite) software. The simulation process involves steps such as protein preparation, preprocessing, refining, system builder, relazing the system, running the simulation and finally analysis of the results. The ligand-protein complex of the 6b obtained from the molecular docking analysis is provided as input to the molecular dynamics calculations. The ligand preparation and protein preprocess is performed. Further, the protein-ligand complex system is optimized and TIP3P solvation model is used by putting the system in an orhohonal box with each direction of 10 Å. Then, this system is neutralized by the addition of appropriate number of counter ions and 0.15 concentration of the NaCl salt was added to the system. The dynamics calculations was performed by subjecting the system to OPLS_2005 force field by relaxing the system at 300 K temperature and pressure of 1.01325 bar in NPT ensemble.

The root mean square deviation (RMSD) is a good indicator of the stability of the protein-ligand complex. If the RMSD of the ligand fluctuates significantly compared with that of the protein, this indicates that the ligand is trying for a new energetically favourable pose other than the pose predicted by the moelcular docking analysis. The protein RMSF is used to evaluate the local changes that takes place for each amino acid with the ligand throughout the simulation period. Further, the nature and period for which these amino acids are in contact with the ligand is analyzed and various other properties associated with the ligand are evaluated [35, 36].

In vitro antibacterial studies

Invitro antibacterial activity was carried out against gram bacteria *Escherichia coli*, via well-established agar diffusion method [37], and zone of inhibition of all the compounds for 200µg of sample was tabulated as below found to be all the molecules exhibited minimal zone of inhibition (Table: 1).

Table1 : Zone of Inhibition for compounds 6a-f against *E.Coli*at 200µg of sample.

Compound Code	<i>E.coli</i>
6a	9.17 +0.29
6b	9.50 +0.50
6c	8.33 +0.58
6d	8.50 +0.50
6e	9.17 +0.29
6f	9.33 +0.58

*Zone of inhibition in mm for 200µg of sample

RESULT & DISCUSSIONS.

Topology analysis

The graphical visualization of the noncovalent interactions exhibited by the compound was carried out using the RDG based NCI isosurface analysis. The RDG isosurfaces and 2D scatter plots with the surface color blue-green-red facilitates to evaluate the nature of the interactions. The 2D scatter plot is drawn by plotting the values of the RDG vs the $\text{sign}(\lambda_2)\rho$. The $\text{sign}(\lambda_2)\rho$ is an indicator of the nature of the interactions [$\text{sign}(\lambda_2)\rho < 0$ for attractive, $\text{sign}(\lambda_2)\rho > 0$ repulsive and $\text{sign}(\lambda_2)\rho$ nearly equals to zero corresponds to the weak van der Waals interactions].

Due to the presence of the similar functional groups, similar type of interactions were observed for the 6a-f series 1-3, 5, and 6. Whereas, for 6d compound, the presence of additional five membered ring with the methyl group attached to the benzene resulted in more number of the hydrogen bonds compared with other compounds. Hence, this design of the compound resulted in the increase in the noncovalent interactions exhibited by the 6d compound.

All the benzene rings in the 6a-f series are found to be associated with a red coloured region in its center, which indicates the steric repulsion exhibited by the compound. Further, the atomic interaction line (AIL) which found to exist between the atoms indicated by light yellow color is associated with a green disc shaped region indicating the presence of weak van der Waals interactions. Further, even in the absence of the AIL between the atoms the green patch is observed this indicates the presence of the non-zero electron density in between atoms. The red spikes in the 2D scatter plot corresponds to the steric repulsion observed in the centers of the benzene, pyrazole and cyclohexane moieties. theisosurface and the 2D scatter plot of all the compounds (6a-f) are given in the Figure 1.

Figure 1 The RDG based isosurface analysis of the compounds: (a): 6a, (b): 6b, (c): 6c, (d): 6d, (e): 6e and (f): 6f.

Molecular docking

In computational docking algorithm, compounds 6a-f were used as a ligand and they are docked with oxidoreductase protein. Exploration on compound-protein interactions and the relative binding affinities for a series of 6 inhibitors provides a good understanding about the binding site of the targeted oxidoreductase protein of *E. coli*. Active site residues of targeted protein were found to be interacting with compounds (6a-f). The binding modes and 2D interactions of targeted protein series complex are shown in Figure 2 and 3. All the compounds are tightly bound into the active pocket of targeted protein, interacting with various interactions such as conventional hydrogen bond, π -donor, π -cation and alkyl interactions with the active site amino acid residues ensuring good binding score (Table: 2). In particular, amino acid Glutamate (GLU A:82) residue is interacting through conventional hydrogen bond interaction with tetra hydro pyron (oxygen) compound is quite common for all (Figure: 2). Among all the compounds 6d shows good binding score of -8.0 kcal/mol with targeted protein. However, the protein showed quite less binding score with the remaining compounds.

Figure 2 Surface (Left) and cartoon (Right) representation of active site of oxidoreductase protein-6a-f series ligands (a): 6a, (b): 6b, (c):6c, (d): 6d, (e): 6e and (f): 6f.

Figure 3 2D binding interactions of oxidoreductase protein-6a-f [(a): 6a, (b): 6b, (c): 6c, (d): 6d, (e): 6e and (f): 6f.] ligand interactions.

Table 2 Interactions involved in the amino acid residue-ligand in the active site of the protein.

Compound Code	Residue involved	Interaction type	Docking score (kcal/mol)	Compound Code	Residue involved	Interaction type	Docking score (kcal/mol)
6a	GLU A:82	Conventional	-7.4	6d	SER A:116	Conventional	-8.0
	SER A:13	Conventional			GLU A:82	Conventional	
	SER A:116	Conventional			SER A:117	Conventional	
	PRO A:81	Alkyl			ASN A:20	Conventional	
	PRO A:81	Alkyl			PRO A:81	Alkyl	
	MET A:118	Alkyl			PRO A:81	Alkyl	
6b	GLU A:82	Conventional	-7.9	6e	GLU A:82	Conventional	-7.3
	SER A:13	Conventional			ILE A:121	Alkyl	
	SER A:116	Conventional			SER A:116	Conventional	
	SER A:117	Pi-Donar			PRO A:81	Alkyl	
	PRO A:81	Alkyl			PRO A:81	Alkyl	
	ILE A:121	Alkyl			SER A:117	Pi-Donar	
	PRO A:81	Alkyl			ILE A:121	Alkyl	
	MET A:118	Alkyl			ARG A:125	Pi-cation	
6c	SER A:116	Conventional	-7.8	6f	GLU A:82	Conventional	-6.5
	GLU A:82	Conventional			SER A:13	Conventional	
	SER A:117	Conventional			SER A:116	Conventional	
	ASN A:20	Conventional			PRO A:81	Alkyl	
	PRO A:81	Alkyl			PRO A:81	Alkyl	
	PRO A:81	Alkyl			MET A:118	Alkyl	

Molecular dynamics simulation analysis

To substantiate the results obtained from the molecular docking results, molecular dynamics simulations of the protein-ligand (6d) complex were performed to study the dynamic behaviour of the interactions between them. The dynamics calculations helps to analyze several factors, such as conformation, stability, radius of gyration, entropies of the ligands. The RMSD plot of the protein-ligand complex is shown in the Figure 4. It is observed that both the protein-ligand are complex have achieved equilibrium throughout the simulation period. The RMSD plot of the protein-ligand complex suggested that the ligand is well within the binding pocket and adhere to the active site of the protein. The RMSD of the protein and ligand fluctuations were found to be well within 2.33 Å and 6.00 Å respectively. Hence, the protein-ligand complex is considered for further analysis. To further understand the protein structures flexibility due to the contact with the ligand root mean square fluctuations study was performed

Figure 4: Very high stable RMSD plot was observed for the protein-ligand complex for a period of 100 ns.

Figure 5: The P-RMSF plot of the protein-ligand complex system with the green lines indicating the amino acids in contact with the ligand.

The RMSF of the $C\alpha$ atoms of the protein over the simulation time indicated that the protein has the fluctuations of about 3.22 Å. The P-RMSF plot is shown in the Figure 2. The green colored vertical lines in the P-RMSF plot indicates the amino acids in contact with the ligand. The fluctuations of the amino acids were found to be: LEU14 (1.31 Å), ARG15 (1.28 Å), GLY17 (1.01 Å), SER18 (0.71 Å), PHE19 (0.59 Å), ASN20 (0.53 Å), PRO81 (0.46 Å), GLU82 (0.48 Å), TYR83 (0.66 Å), ASN84 (0.91 Å), TYR85 (0.75 Å), SER116 (0.48 Å), SER117 (0.57 Å), MET118 (0.73 Å), GLY119 (0.85 Å), VAL120 (0.87 Å), ILE152 (0.56 Å) and GLN153 (0.69 Å). The maximum fluctuations was observed for the PRO81 amino acid with 0.46 Å. As the fluctuations observed was less indicates greater stability of the protein-ligand complex. Further, the type of interactions exhibited by the amino acids with the protein is explored using the PL-contact map as shown in the Figure 3. The PL-contact map provides valuable insights into the time for which a particular amino acid in contact with the protein will have the particular type of interactions. Various types of interactions were observed and ASN84 is found to have hydrogen bond interactions with the ligand for about 0.91% of the simulation time. Further, the ASN84 is found to have multiple type of contacts such as ionic and water bridges with the compound. The TYR83 had three contacts such with the majority being the hydrophobic type of interactions with the contact time of 0.87% of total simulation time (water bridges for 11.7% and 0.2% for hydrogen type of interactions). Further, the amino acids such as ARG15 (5.6%), PHE19 (24.3%), ASN20 (31.7%), GLU82 (20.8%), TYR85 (50.0%), SER116 (22.0%), SER117 (2.9%), MET118 (2.0%) and GLY119 (1.0%). The amino acids such as ARG15 (4.7%) and SER18 (1.9%) found to have ionic type of interactions with the compound.

Figure 6: The protein-ligand contact map revealing the time for which the particular amino acid in contact with the ligand (left part) and the color code indicates the type of total number of contacts each amino acids has during the simulation period of 100 ns.

Figure 7: Torsional plots of the compound indicating the rotation of the bonds during the simulation period of 100 ns.

To understand the torsional changes in the ligand during the simulation period of 100 ns. The torsional profile of the ligand is assigned with a particular color and the changes observed in the bonds is shown in the Figure 7. The torsional profile indicated that the compound underwent conformational change to retain the protein bound conformation. Further, various ligand properties such as RMSD, rGyr (radius of gyration), IntraHB (Intra molecular hydrogen bonding), MoISA, SASA and PSA are shown in the Figure 5. The RMSD and rGyr is found to achieve equilibrium at 1.9 Å and 5.1 Å respectively. No intramolecular hydrogen formation was observed during the overall simulation period which is indicated in the Figure 8. The other ligand properties such as MoISA, SASA and PSA were evaluated and they are found to achieve equilibrium at 346 Å², 240 Å² and 120 Å² respectively. The 2D representation of the ligand-protein contact is shown in the Figure 6 keeping the contact strength at 30%. It is observed that both TYR85 and ASN20 forms water bridges with the ligand. Whereas, the ASN84 is found to have hydrogen bond interactions with the ligand

Figure 8: The study of the various properties of ligand during the simulation period of 100 ns.

Figure 9 The ligand-protein contact of the complex revealing the amino acids in contact with the ligand as visualized at 30% of minimum contact strength.

CONCLUSIONS

The scheme of the synthesized series of novel pyrazole derivatives is given. Spectral investigations were used to determine the structure of all synthesized compounds. All the compounds were analyzed using, ^1H NMR, and LCMS, RDG based isosurface analysis of the compounds revealed crucial information regarding the noncovalent interactions exhibited by the compounds. The presence of the substituent ($\text{SO}_2\text{-CH}_3$) attached to the benzene moiety in the 6d compound shows more noncovalent interactions compared to other compounds. The molecular docking analysis of the compounds were performed against the oxidoreductase protein (3SLV) showed good binding affinities. Further, the compound 6d showed the highest binding score of -8.0 kcal/mol, this is in accordance with the large noncovalent interactions. The molecular dynamics results revealed that the 6d is found to be well within the binding pocket of the protein for overall simulation period of 100 ns. Further, the low fluctuations of the amino acids in contact with the protein substantiated the high stability of the ligand-protein complex. Even though cyclization reaction involving HCl salt of 1-(terhydro-2H-pyran-4-yl)-1,2,4,5,6,7-hexahydro-3H-pyrazolo[3,4-c]pyridine-3-one with isocyanates found to yield compounds in good yield the extraction process was bit difficulty and separations from column chromatography consumes more time and cost. Hydrogen bonded interaction seems to be strongest mode of binding was observed to be absent in molecular docking and further it can be extended to other *invitro* pharmacological studies by establishing their binding energies through molecular docking studies.

Key findings

- Cyclisation reaction of tert-butyl- 4-methyl 3-oxopiperidine-1,4-dicarboxylate with the pyrone hydrazine shown access the potent piperidine fused pyrazolone scaffold with excellent yield
- Molecular dynamics simulations were performed to find the vicinity of docked ligand and protein.
- DFT studies established the physiochemical parameters of synthesized compounds.

Funding

'This research had no external funding' no financial support was received.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors are thankful to Sri Siddhartha Academy of Higher Education (SSAHE) and Karnataka Council for Technological Upgradation (KCTU) for rendering all the facilities to carry out the research work and also the authors are thankful to the DST-FIST (SR/FST/PSI-119/2019), National Single Crystal Diffractometer Facility, DoS in Physics..

Conflict of interest

'The authors declare no conflict of interest'.

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